

RESEARCH PAPER

OPEN ACCESS

Morphological characteristics of the Philippines CARAGA black native chicken

Tomas M. Austral Jr^{*1}, Benecar B. Olaybar¹, Shernelyn S. Palma², Escolastico S. Cagatin², Lutess C. Gallardo¹

¹*Department of Agricultural Science, College of Agriculture and Allied Industries, Caraga State University, Ampayon, Butuan City, Philippines*

²*Department of Agriculture, Trento, Agusan del Sur, Philippines*

Article published on November 15, 2022

Key words: Morphological characteristics, Breeding, Purification, Black coloration

Abstract

The study was performed to describe the morphological characteristics of the Caraga black native chicken. A total of 40 heads of the native chickens (8 roosters and 32 hens) were used. The test animals are the product of the breeding and purification project of the Caraga black native chicken. The result of the morphological characteristics shows a predominant black coloration on the significant body parts of the native chicken, such as black plumage, black comb, black air lobe, black shank, black skin color, dark-brown Iris, dark grey beak, grayish meat, black bones, and black wattle shanks. Moreover, quantitative body measurements on 12-month-old native chicken recorded that the rooster is heavier (1.9Kg), taller (33cm), and has a higher body length (24cm) than the hen (weight = 1,350g, height = 28.5cm, body length = 24cm). Based on the findings, hens are generally smaller than roosters, which can be attributed to the body build of roosters. Males, naturally, are suited for muscle building, while the hens' body is built for reproduction.

*Corresponding Author: Tomas M. Austral ✉ tomaaustraljr@gmail.com

Introduction

As an archipelagic country, the Philippines has more than 7,100 islands. Despite introducing exotic commercial breeds and hybrids of chickens, in the year 2000, more than 50% of the chicken population was still composed of native and upgraded types. Some of these native chickens are: 'Banaba,' 'Bolinao,' 'Camarines,' and 'Paroakan' (Lambio, 2000). As early as 1998, the role of native chickens in the Philippine economy has been recognized. The Philippine native chickens' ability to produce meat and eggs under minimal management, intervention, and feeding inputs is why the Philippines' native chicken has been the primary source of meat and eggs for Filipino farmers (Dusaran, and Cabarles, 2005; Dusaran RN, and Pabulayan, 2012). Moreover, native chickens have higher muscle mass, less fat (Alano, 2015), and unique taste, flavor, texture, and nutraceutical compounds. That is why the price of the native chickens' meat and eggs are higher than commercial meat- and egg-type chickens (Lambio, 2000).

The Philippines is considered one of the biodiversity hotspots in the Indo-Australian Archipelago (Myers *et al.*, 2000). Six (6) out of 243 recorded local poultry breeds in Asia could be found in the Philippines (Gaither and Rocha, 2013). However, limited studies were conducted on native chicken. To address this issue, the Department of Science and Technology-Philippine Council for Agriculture and Natural Resources Research and Aquatic Development (PCAARRD) launched and funded projects purposely for research, preservation of the species, instruction, dispersal to farmers, and commercialization of the product and the Philippines native chicken (Godinez *et al.*, 2021). Because of the help of DOST-PCAARRD, six Philippine native breeds were identified and studied. These are the Banaba chicken in Southern Tagalog, the Camarines chicken in Bicol, the Darag chicken in Panay Island, the Boholano chicken in Bohol, the Bolinao native chicken in Ilocos region, and the Zamboanga Peninsula (ZamPen) native chicken in Zamboanga. These native chicken strains underwent purification with the help of the DOST-PCAARRD (Sarian, 2019). Aside from the six identified and

purified Philippine native chickens, another study on the new breed of native chicken endemic in the Caraga region was conducted in 2019. The Caraga black native chicken is locally known as Patani.

The Caraga Black Native Chicken known as Patani is endemic in the Caraga region. This native chicken possessed distinct morphological traits among the identified Philippine native chickens because of its black plumage, skin, and shank. Further, it has a unique taste, less body fat, and can quickly adapt to the changing environmental conditions of the Caraga Region. However, this genetic group is in small number, and this might be attributed to crossbreeding of other native genetic groups. Hence, conservation measures must be implemented through intensive breeding and selection and the phenotypic characterization of the Caraga black native chicken. It was common knowledge in the field of breeding and purification that for research and preservation of the Philippines native chicken to be successful, phenotypic characterization is necessary. Phenotypic characterization/ morphological characteristics is the method of identifying distinct breed populations and describing their characteristics and those of their production environments (Rogelio *et al.*, 2013).

This study studied the Caraga black native chicken's phenotypic characterization, morphological characteristics, and morphometric characteristics. The morphological features include the plumage pattern, skin color, shank color, comb type, and earlobe color. Moreover, a quantitative body measurement consists of the body length, shank length, wingspan, and chest circumference.

Materials and methods

Locale of the Study

The study was conducted in the Organic Native Chicken Project area, Caraga State University-Main Campus. The facilities consist of one breeder house, seven grower cages, six brooder boxes, one incubator, and one hatcher. The house design was from Iloilo's Darag native chicken breeder house. It has eight cages, and every cage sized 245cm × 120cm × 350cm.

Each coop has three nests positioned at the same level or height. The grower cage measured 400cm x 400cm, and the brooder boxes were sized 127cm x 82cm x 52cm with 50 watts incandescent bulb. Flooring filled with rice hulls.

Test Animals

A total of 40 heads (8 roosters, 38 hens) of native chicken from the F1 generation of the breeding and purification project of the Caraga black native chicken were subjected to phenotypic and morphological characteristics.

Morphological Classification and Data Analysis

Morphological characteristics and morphometric measurements of the CARAGA black native chicken were based on the FAO Animal Production and Health Guidelines No. 11: Phenotypic Characterization of Animal Genetic Resources (FAO, 2011). Morphological characteristics include feathering characteristics covering only plumage patterns, while skin characteristics considered skin color, shank color, comb type, and earlobe color. The average quantitative body measurements, including weight, height, body length, shank length, wingspan, chest circumference, primary feathers, and secondary, were calculated using Microsoft Excel 2016.

Results and discussion

Morphological characteristics

Qualitative traits such as plumage color, comb color, earlobe color, shank color, skin color, earlobe, and wattle color manifest the dominant black coloration in both hen and rooster. The hen and rooster have the same dark brown iris. Moreover, the hen and rooster display the same plain plumage pattern, upright body carriage, and single comb type, as reflected in Table 1.

Table 1. Morphological characteristics of hen and rooster of Caraga black native chicken.

Morphological Characteristics	Rooster	Hen
Plumage	Black	Black
Plumage Pattern	Plain	Plain
Body Carriage	Upright	Upright
Comb Type	Single	Cushion
Comb Color	Black	Black
Earlobe Color	Black	Black
Shank Color	Black	Black
Skin Color	Black	Black
Iris Color	Dark Brown	Dark Brown
Beak Color	Black	Black

Compared to the four genetic groups of the Philippine native chickens, the Caraga native chickens manifest the distinct feature attributed to the black coloration on most of its morphological characteristics (Table 2, Fig. 1).

Table 2. The morphological characteristics of the five genetic groups of Philippines native chickens.

Parameters	Mean	Min.	Max.
Hen			
Body Weight (Kg)	1.35	1.25	1.45
Height (cm)	23	22	24
Body Length (cm)	19.5	19	20
Wingspan (cm)	64	62	66
Shank Length (cm)	8.25	7.5	9
Chest Circumference (cm)	30	28	32
Primary Feathers	14	14	14
Secondary Feathers (cm)	17.5	16	19
Roosters			
Body Weight (Kg)	1.90	1.6	2.2
Height (cm)	28.5	27	30
Body Length (cm)	24	23	25
Wingspan (cm)	77	74	80
Shank Length (cm)	10.5	10	11
Chest Circumference (cm)	33.5	33	34
Primary Feathers (cm)	16.5	15	18
Secondary Feathers (cm)	20	17	23

Fig. 1. The rooster and hen of the Caraga Black Native Chicken.

The native chicken's black coloration on its dermis and tissues is the mutation called fibromatosis. Fibromelanosis is the abnormal accumulation of the dark pigment melanin in the avian body's dermis and connective tissue formations. Fibromelanosis (Fm) is due to an autosomal dominant gene(s) called endothelin three or EDN3. (Lukanov and Genchev, 2013; Bittel, 2019).

Endothelin 3 (EDN3), mostly found in vertebrates, is the one that controls the skin color. The endothelin 3 (EDN3) is the reason for migrating melanoblasts, or cells responsible for creating color.

In hyperpigmented chickens, all the chickens' body cells show or release EDN3, resulting in up to 10 times as many melanoblasts and black pigment on the chicken's dermis (Bittel, 2019).

Quantitative Body Measurements

The quantitative body measurements of a 12-month-old Caraga black native chicken show that a rooster is heavier, taller, and has a higher body length than a hen. Rooster with an average weight of 1.9Kg, a height of 33cm, body length of 24cm, wing span of 77cm, shank length of 10.5cm, chest circumference of 33.5cm, primary feathers of 16.5cm, and secondary feathers 20cm. The hen, on the other hand, has a body weight of 1.35Kg, height of 28.5cm, body length of 19.5cm, a wingspan of 64cm, shank length of 8.25cm, a chest circumference of 30cm, primary feathers of 14cm and Secondary feathers of 17.5 as shown in Table 3.

In most birds, males are more prominent. The ideal size of the male in most species of higher vertebrates, including birds, was that the males compete with one other for mates. In these struggles, those that are larger or stronger than the average will have an advantage. They will secure more mates and leave more offspring. Hence, Darwin claimed that the larger size of the males of most birds and mammals is the result of adaptation (Darwin, 1874). Among the five genetic groups of Philippine native chickens, Patani is the heaviest both rooster and hen (R = 1.9Kg, H = 1.35Kg) have the longest wing span (R = 77cm, H= 64cm), and the highest chest circumference (R = 33.5cm, H = 30cm). In terms of height, the Patani rooster is the tallest at 28.5 while both Zampen and Darag hens are the tallest at 24cm, and for the body length, the Darag rooster and hen obtained the highest body length (R = 43cm, H = 38cm), Table 4.

Table 3. Quantitative body measurements of Caraga black native chicken.

Morphological Characteristics	Genetic Group of Philippine Native Chickens									
	Patani		Zampen		Boholanon		Camarines		Darag	
	R	H	R	H	R	H	R	H	R	H
Plumage	Black	Black	Black w/ Red	Black	Wine Red	Red	Yellow-Orange	Brown	Red	Yellow-Brown
Plumage Pattern	Plain	Plain	Plain	Plain	Plain	Laced	Bared	Laced	Plain	Laced
Body Carriage	Upright	Upright	Upright	Upright	Slightly upright	Slightly upright	–	–	Slightly upright	Slightly upright
Comb Type	Single	Single	Pea	Pea	Single	Single	Single	Single	Single	Single
Comb Color	Black	Black	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Earlobe Color	Black	Black	Red	Red	Red	Reddish White	Red	Red	White	White
Shank Color	Black	Black	Yellow/ Gray	Gray	White	Yellow	White/ Gray	White/ Gray	Gray	Gray
Skin Color	Black	Black	White	White	White	White	White	White	White	White
Iris Color	Dark Brown	Dark Brown	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange	Orange
Beak Color	Black	Black	Black	Yellow	Black	Yellow	White	White	White	Gray

Legend: R = Rooster, H = Hen

Table 4. The Quantitative body measurements of the five genetic groups of Philippines native chickens.

Morphological Characteristics	Genetic Group of Philippine Native Chickens									
	Patani		Zampen		Boholanon		Camarines		Darag	
	R	H	R	H	R	H	R	H	R	H
Body Weight (kg)	1.9	1.35	1.29	1.1	0.82	0.75	1.1	0.9	1.50	1.2
Height (cm)	28.5	23	24	24	21	20	26	22	24	20
Body Length (cm)	24	19.5	43	39	35	34	21.3	17.4	43	38
Wingspan (cm)	77	64	45	41	42	41	41	41	49.5	41
Shank Length (cm)	10.5	8.25	11	9	9.7	9.5	7.1	5.6	11.6	8.6
Chest Circumference (cm)	33.5	30	31	29	24.6	24	25	23	31	28

Aside from Patani, two chickens exhibit fibromelanosis or hyperpigmentation. The Silkie chicken of China and the Ayam Cemani of Indonesia. The Silkie chicken has

been a melanocyte precursor and neural crest migration model. The selkie breed is believed to have been established before the 13th century (Haw, 2006).

Unlike Patani, Silkie chicken is named for the hair-like appearance of adult feathers. Silkie pigmentation is found extensively in the dermal layer of skin, sheaths of muscles and nerves, tendons, gut mesenteries, blood vessel walls, trachea, and air sacs (Kuklenski, 1915; Hutt, 1949; Faraco *et al.*, 2001; Dorshorst *et al.*, 2010). According to Hutt, 1949, 2 genes control 1949, the hyperpigmentation of Silkie chicken, autosomal dominant fibromelanosis (Fm/fm⁺) and the sex-linked incompletely dominant inhibitor of dermal melanin (Id/id⁺).

It was found that id⁺ allows pigment of the shank in the dermal layer of skin, and junctions with Fm cause the hyperpigmentation in the Silkie chicken. The hyperpigmentation phenotype of the Silkie chicken is believed to be caused by abnormal migration and proliferation of NCCs, the multipotent precursors of the melanocyte, in the developing embryo (Lecoin *et al.*, 1996; Reedy *et al.*, 1998; Faraco *et al.*, 1998; Dorshorst *et al.*, 2010). Endothelin 3 (EDN3) as a candidate gene for FM and beta 1, 4- Galactosyltransferase, polypeptide 1 (B4GALT1), and version (VCAN) as candidate genes for Id (Dorshorst *et al.*, 2010).

Ayam Cemani is a breed of chickens with characteristics of black plumage, comb and wattles, beak, eyes, skin and legs, and even black internal organs, bones, and muscles. Ayam Cemani is raised for eggs and meat to meet domestic market needs. In Java, Ayam Cemani is used in ritual ceremonies and folk medicine to treat cardiovascular and respiratory diseases (Muryanto, 1991, Iskandar *et al.*, 2005; Lukasiewicz, 2015; Dharmayanthi *et al.*, 2017).

Ayam Cemani also exhibits fibromelanosis or dermal hyperpigmentation and possesses complex segmental duplications on chromosome 20 that involve the endothelin three genes, EDN3. A genomic region, DR1 OF 127kb, and another region, DR2 OF 171kb, were duplicated by unequal crossing over, accompanied by inversion of one DR2. The findings of the quantitative PCR and copy number variation analyses on the Cemani genome sequence show the EDN3 duplication. These genetic arrangements are

identical in Cemani and Silkie, manifesting a single origin of the genetic cause of Fm. The two DR1s harbor two distinct EDN3 haplotypes in the form of permanent heterozygosity (Dharmayanthi *et al.*, 2017). Unlike the Silkie chicken of China and the Ayam Cemani, a study on the possible reason for the hyperpigmentation of the Patani is still unavailable. The findings on the morphological features of the Patani manifest similarity of the hyperpigmentation of the Silkie chicken of China and the Ayam Cemani.

Conclusion

The result shows that the Patani possessed distinct traits among the five genetic groups of Philippine native chicken. The eumelanin on the morphological features of the Patani might be the reason for its distinctive characteristics. Moreover, the Patani rooster is heavier compared to the female Patani because males compete with one other for mates. Darwin claimed that the larger size of the males of most birds and mammals results from adaptation due to competition [13]. Furthermore, the possible causative agent behind the hyperpigmentation of the Patani might be similar to the causative agent on the hyperpigmentation of the Silkie Chicken and Ayam Cemani.

Acknowledgements

The Department of Science and Technology financially supported this research- Philippine Council for Agriculture, Aquatic and Natural Resources Research and Development (DOST-PCAARRD).

References

- Alano J.** 2015. Native Chicken: the healthiest chicken for Filipinos [Internet][cited 2022 May 1]. Available from <https://filipinohealthline.com/2019/09/07/native-chicken-health-benefits/>.
- Bittel J.** 2019. This chicken has black bones, organs, and meat: Here's why [Internet] [cited 2022 July 20]. Available from: <https://api.nationalgeographic.com/distribution/public/amp/animals/2019/09/why-black-chickens-fibromelanosis?>
- Darwin CR.** 1874. The descent of man, and selection in relation to sex. 2d ed. Appleton, New York 1874.

- Dharmayanthi AB, Terai Y, Sulandari S, Zein MS, Akiyama T, Satta Y.** 2017. The origin and evolution of fibromelanosis in domesticated chickens: genomic comparison of Indonesian Cemani and Chinese Silkie breeds. *Plos one* **12(4)**, e0173147.
- Dorshorst B, Okimoto R, Ashwell C.** 2010. Genomic regions associated with dermal hyperpigmentation, polydactyly and other morphological traits in the Silkie chicken. *Journal of Heredity* **101(3)**, 339-50.
- Dusaran RN, Pabulayan RAV.** 2012. Production practices of the native chicken growers in Western Visayas. *Patubas* **7(1)**, 40-65.
- Dusaran R, Cabarles J.** 2005. Native chicken production study in the top three native chicken producing municipalities of Iloilo. Research report submitted to the University Research Center, Central Philippine University, Iloilo City.
- Faraco CD, Vaz SA, Pástor MV, Erickson CA.** 2001. Hyperpigmentation in the Silkie fowl correlates with abnormal migration of fate-restricted melanoblasts and loss of environmental barrier molecules. *Developmental dynamics: an official publication of the American Association of Anatomists* **220(3)**, 212-25.
- Food and Agriculture Organizations.** 2011. Phenotypic characterization of animal genetic resources FAO.
- Gaither MR, Rocha LA.** 2013. Origins of species richness in the Indo-Malay-Philippine biodiversity hotspot: Evidence for the centre of overlap hypothesis. *Journal of Biogeography* **40(9)**, 1638-1648.
- Godinez CJP, Dadios PJD, Espina DM, Matsunaga M, Nishibori M.** 2021. Population Genetic Structure and Contribution of Philippine Chickens to the Pacific Chicken Diversity Inferred From Mitochondrial DNA. *Frontiers in Genetics* **12**.
- Haw SG.** 2006. Marco Polo's China: a Venetian in the realm of Khubilai Khan. Routledge.
- Hutt FB.** 1949. Genetics of the fowl. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- Iskandar S, Seapudin Y.** 2005. Germplasm, Cemani chicken (qualitative characteristics, quantitative characteristics, breeding procedure, preservation and research efforts). Available: www.balitnak.litbang.deptan.go.id
- Kuklenski J.** 1915. Über das vorkommen und die verteilung des pigmentes in den organen und gewebe bei japanischen seidenhühnern. *Cohen*.
- Lambio AL.** 2000. Philippine native chickens. *Philippine Agricultural Scientist (Philippines)*.
- Lecoin L, Gabella G, Le Douarin N.** 1996. Origin of the c-kit-positive interstitial cells in the avian bowel. *Development* **122(3)**, 725-33.
- Lukanov H, Genchev A.** 2013. Fibromelanosis in domestic chickens. *Agricultural Science and Technology* **5(3)**, 239-46.
- Lukasiewicz M, Niemiec J, Wnuk A, Mroczek-Sosnowska N.** 2015. Meat quality and the histological structure of breast and leg muscles in Ayam Cemani chickens, Ayam Cemani × Sussex hybrids and slow-growing Hubbard JA 957 chickens. *Journal of the Science of Food and Agriculture* **95(8)**, 1730-5.
- Muryanto M.** 1991. *Malajah poultry Indonesia* No. **132/XII**, pp. 16-20.
- Myers N, Mittermeier RA, Mittermeier CG, Da Fonseca GA, Kent J.** 2000. Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities. *Nature* **403(6772)**, 853-858.
- Reedy MV, Faraco CD, Erickson CA.** 1998. Specification and migration of melanoblasts at the vagal level and in hyperpigmented Silkie chickens. *Developmental dynamics: an official publication of the American Association of Anatomists* **213(4)**, 476-85.

Rogelio Jr VL, Lambio AL, Vega RS, De Guia AP. 2013. Phenotypic characterization of native chicken in Palawan, Philippines. *Philippine Journal of Veterinary and Animal Sciences* 39(2).

Sarian Z. 2019. Do your own experiment: Purify your own native chicken; it can be challenging, rewarding, at times frustrating. *Agri News*. Retrieved from <https://zacsarian.com/do-your-own-experiment-purify-your-own-native-chicken-it-can-be-challenging-rewarding-at-times-frustrating/>